

ARIA Open Science Policy

Aligning Research to Impact Autism (ARIA) is an initiative to accelerate scientific discovery and create more therapeutic opportunities for people with profound autism and people on the spectrum who seek additional support. ARIA connects emerging research, insights, and promising technologies from across scientific fields, to build an integrated ecosystem that bridges clinical and translational research.

The ARIA Open Science Policy aims to maximize the impact and reusability of research outputs, thereby fostering an efficient and trustworthy research ecosystem that accelerates scientific discovery.

The Policy comprises three overarching requirements and applies to all work partially or fully funded by ARIA. The Policy will be operationalized into a Handbook, which will be linked to from ariaroadmap.org, and used to support and monitor compliance.

Policy Requirements

1. Deposit Research Outputs

Requirement: All research outputs generated as part of an ARIA-funded study must be deposited to a community-recognized repository. Individual-level human participant data must be deposited in accordance with a project's Data Transfer Plan.

Research outputs to deposit include:

- Prospective study registrations and detailed study protocols – *mandatory*
- Lab materials (e.g., cell lines, organisms, reagents, antibodies) – *if generated*
- Biosamples – *if generated*
- Experimental protocols, methods, and procedures – *mandatory*
- Raw data (unprocessed data, as collected) – *if generated*
- Code and scripts used to preprocess and clean data – *if generated*
- Cleaned data (processed, quality-controlled data) – *mandatory*
- Code and scripts used to analyze and visualize data – *mandatory*

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- Algorithms, AI models, and other tools – *if generated*
 - Preprints – *mandatory*
 - Peer review – *when available and appropriate*
 - Journal publications – *if generated*

2. Ensure Immediate Access

Requirement: All research outputs generated as part of an ARIA-funded study must be licensed to allow for unrestricted reuse (other than individual-level human participant data), be accompanied with rich metadata (e.g., in accordance with [FAIR Principles](#)), and be made immediately available at the time they are produced, or are ready to deposit, not only at the time of publishing a manuscript in a journal (see Policy Requirement 1 for a list of research outputs). Individual-level human participant data must be immediately shared in accordance with a project's Data Transfer Plan and allow for controlled-access rights to bona fide researchers in perpetuity.

Implementation:

- Access may be restricted and/or delayed to the extent required to comply with ethical guidelines, privacy requirements, and Institutional Review Board approval, and to safeguard study integrity (e.g., prevent breaking a blind)
- Recommended reuse terms for research outputs include CC0 (non-sensitive data), CC BY (text-based documents), MIT (code), and OpenMTA (biological materials)

3. Identify Research Resources

Requirement: All research resources used and generated in a study must be unambiguously identified in relevant documents (e.g., in preprints, study protocols, analysis scripts).

Implementation:

- Maintain a Key Resources Table and use Availability Statements to identify where all research resources used and generated in the study can be accessed (see Policy Requirement 1 for a list of research resources)
- Use persistent identifiers when citing research resources (e.g., DOIs, RRIDs, accession numbers) and identifying research contributors (ORCIDiDs)

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- In all research outputs, acknowledge ARIA funding and include an ARIA author affiliation for ARIA-funded contributors

Compliance

Compliance with the ARIA Open Science Policy is a condition of ARIA funding. Adherence to this policy will be monitored and factored into decisions about:

- Continuation of current grants
- Eligibility for supplemental funding
- Consideration for future ARIA funding opportunities
- Recognition within the ARIA network

ARIA staff will work collaboratively with grantees to support compliance and address challenges. If barriers to compliance arise, grantees should contact ARIA staff as early as possible to discuss solutions.